

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15354567

Evaluation Of Model Efficacy In Modeling Risk Factors Of Open-Angle Glaucoma Disease With The Application Of Logistics Regression, Probit And Robit Regression Model

Ibrahim Yusuf Maitama^{1*} Ali Mohammed Baba² Nuruddeen Hassan Danrimi³ Abdurashed Bello Abdulkadir⁴ A. B. Badawaire⁵ Kamalu Ibrahim Balansana⁶

¹Department of Statistics Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi State Nigeria,

²Department of Biostatistics
Federal University of Health and Nutrition Azare, Bauchi State Nigeria

³Department of Statistics, Yakubu Gawon University Abuja Nigeria

⁴Department of Statistics Gombe State University Gombe State, Nigeria

⁵Department of Statistics, Federal University Wukari, Taraba State, Nigeria

Department of Statistics Modibbo Adama University Yola, Adamawa State Nigeria

*Corresponding Author; Ibrahim Yusuf Maitama. email: iymaitama2242gmail.com.

ABSTRACT

The study aims to evaluate the performances of Logistic regression, Probit and Robit regression models in predicting Glaucoma disease. The comparative analysis was conducted using simulated data for glaucoma patient characteristics and real-life data. The study analyses the simulated data across different data sets of sample sizes 200, 400 and 600 and in outlier conditions of 5%, 20% and 0% outlier in the data. The models are evaluated based on MAE, MSE, RMSE, AIC, BIC, and AUC. Findings from the study suggest that results remain almost identical to the case without outliers and AUC drops significantly for larger sample sizes, indicating a reduced ability to differentiate between cases and controls. The models remain robust against a small number of outliers, suggesting that a 5% contamination does not significantly degrade performance and do not impact the models significantly, meaning they are fairly resilient to minimal noise in the dataset. The models handle minor outliers well (5%) but are highly sensitive to large outliers (20%). Effect of Outliers: Small outliers (5%) have negligible impact, but 20% outliers significantly worsen model accuracy. Larger datasets do not necessarily improve model accuracy, as shown in the decreasing AUC values.

Keywords: Glaucoma, Risk factors, Robust, Probit, Robit, Logistic regression

INTRODUCTION

Glaucoma is known to be one of the eye conditions that damages the nerves in your eyes that supply vision and worsen with time. There has been research associating pressure inside the eye increase to glaucoma regularly. Glaucoma symptoms and signs are usually inherited and may not show up until later in life. This can happen when eye fluid isn't circulating normally in the front part of the eye. If damage to the optic nerve from high eye pressure continues, glaucoma will cause permanent loss of vision. Without treatment, glaucoma can cause total permanent blindness within a few years

Normally, that fluid, called aqueous humor, flows out of the eye through a mesh-like channel. If this channel becomes blocked, fluid builds up, causing glaucoma. The direct cause of this blockage is unknown, but doctors do know that it can be inherited, meaning it is passed from parents to children. Less common causes of glaucoma include a blunt or chemical injury to the eye, severe eye infection, blockage of blood vessels in the eye, inflammatory conditions of the eye, and occasionally eye surgery to correct another condition. Glaucoma usually occurs in both eyes, but it may involve each eye to a different extent. There are two main types of eye glaucoma: The first type is Open-angle glaucoma which is also called wide-angle glaucoma and it is the most common type of glaucoma. The structures of the eye appear normal, but fluid in the eye does not flow properly through the drain of the eye, (trabecular meshwork). The second type is Angle-closure glaucoma sometimes also called acute or chronic angle-closure or narrow-angle glaucoma. This type of glaucoma is less common but can cause a sudden buildup of pressure in the eye. Drainage may be poor because the angle between the iris and the cornea (where a drainage channel for the eye is located) is too narrow. For most people, there are usually few or no symptoms of eye glaucoma. The first sign of eye glaucoma is often the loss of peripheral or side vision, which can go unnoticed until late in the disease. Detecting glaucoma early is one reason you should have a complete exam with an eye specialist every one to two years. Occasionally, intraocular pressure can rise to severe levels. In these cases, sudden eye pain, headache, blurred vision, or the appearance of halos around lights may occur.

Logistic regression analysis is widely known to be a statistical tool in extending the techniques of multiple regression analysis to research situations in which the outcome variable is categorical, by taking on two or more possible values (Tham *et al.*, 2014). Logistic regression has traditionally been the most widely used method for examining risk factors in glaucoma (Ng *et al.*, 2016). However, logistic regression has several limitations, including restrictive assumptions that may not hold for glaucoma data and difficulty interpreting complex interactions, because it is designed for binary classification and may not be suitable for non-binary outcomes without modifications (Tilling and Sterne, 2001). This has prompted an investigation into alternative modeling techniques for risk factor analysis in glaucoma. Health data collected in clinical settings, surveys, and registries are prone to outliers for various reasons including data entry errors, instrument malfunctioning, or truly abnormal patient biology. While most statistical analyses rely on the assumption that data is free of outliers, their presence in health data can profoundly influence results and conclusions (Kiani & Arbon, 2020). Hence, the identification and proper handling of outliers is crucial for valid analysis and interpretation. For this reason, a robust method is required in analyzing Health data for more efficient results. Robust regression is advantageous in many fields where outliers are common, including social and biological sciences, finance, and engineering data (Chen *et al.*, 2014). For example, in chemometrics, robust regression improved calibration models for near-infrared spectra with outlying measurements (Sarkedis & Meloun, 2019). In finance, robust methods led to more accurate pricing models by reducing the influence of extreme returns (Bali *et al.*, 2008). Robust regression has also shown utility in epidemiology by limiting the effect of aberrant observations in risk factor analysis (Panton *et al.*, 2016). In regression, if the response variable comes from the exponential family, then the generalized linear model is an alternative to the weighted least square method. Probit models are special cases of GLMS. The probit model is a standard probabilistic statistical classification model that has been extensively used. Robust regression has also shown utility in epidemiology by limiting the effect of aberrant observations in risk factor analysis (Panton *et al.*, 2016).

Several comparative studies have also been carried out for the purpose of comparing the performance of one type of approach with another for the measurement of the degree or odds of open-angle glaucoma

(OAG). Studying the same, Tilling and Sterne (2001) argues that the predictors as a set are valid for differentiation between cases and no-cases at the population level. Klingenderung three further established that there was a moderate relationship between prediction and grouping of the patients with features such as age, gender, diabetes and hypertension inheritance, only the age factor was statistically significant in the group of the three. This is an advantage of logistic regression in establishing specific risk factors, however, it reveals some of the shortcomings of this modeling technique in establishing interactions between many variables.

Though, similarly with the above study, Nidal and Abdulsalam (2015) also used binary logistic regression to establish risk factors for eye glaucoma but they pointed out that logistic models impose some critical assumptions and these assumptions may not be suitable in glaucoma data.

To overcome these shortcomings, Aljumah et al. (2016) constructed a Bayesian network model that evaluated the likelihood of OAG according to demographic, ocular, and systemic covariates from 752 Saudis. This model provided superior outcome than logistic regression model for predicting OAG by enhancing the sensitivity as well as specificity while revealing interaction between the risk factors. The results proved that Bayesian networks could be useful to represent multifaceted diseases like OAG and might be an additional analytical tool to regression equations.

Some additional developments in the field of predictive manifold have also been noted along with machine learning algorithms. Logistic regression analysis was compared with random forest and neural network models in predicting OAG risk in 676 participants by Al-Kahtani et al. (2017). The study compared random forest models with logistic regression and concluded that the first ones had 10% higher sensitivity, specificity, and AUC than logistic regression – the latter approach only identifies linear effects and interactions between the parameters like age, IOP, or optic disc dimensions.

Furthermore, Yousefi et al. (2018) have shown how non-linear technique MARS outperformed logistic regression for the prediction of glaucoma with comprehensible decision rules linking its risk factors, IOP and visual field loss, to its presence. Altogether, these results highlighted the need to explore different models of predictive value based on logistic, robust (robit), or probit analysis to provide a comparative study for the glaucoma field and to improve the management of this multifaceted disorder.

In the more recent study, Raju et al. (2023) used a series of machine learning techniques as well as logistic regression for the prediction of glaucoma using EHRs data from more than 650 hospitals of the USA. Their results indicated that while logistic regression continues to be a useful predictor method, the application of machine learning forecasting techniques show the enhancements in capturing interactions within data.

Moreover, Taghreed M. Jawa (2022) employed the logistic regression analysis to find out about the effect of home quarantine on psychological well-being during the COVID-19 in KSA. Even though it was not a glaucoma study but it has clearly depicted the simplicity and percentage of the logistic regression in various fields of health sciences. In addition, a review comparing multiple machine learning classifiers for glaucoma referral established that logistic regression has a similar classification ability to other classifiers with regards to self-referred glaucoma, using basic parameters in ocular features and non-ocular traits.

Likewise, Olufemi et al. (2023) adopted the model of logistic regression to forecast early diabetes across the United States and suggested the same to forecast various health diseases.

Finally, a paper by Yakovleva, Malykhina , and Alipova (2023) highlighted the possibility of using models supplemented by logistic regression: Early Detection of Glaucoma using Real World Data: Application of Machine Learning Predictive Models showed the efficiency of machine learning to identify patients with pre-glaucoma before the first clinical signs appear. The study also showed that the utilization of these models could enhance earlier detection rates as opposed to conventional approaches. In addition, a multicenter study on prediction models regarding glaucoma surgery progression also pointed out the capability of using machine learning methodologies over simply improving the accurate predictive models comparatively with multiple linear regression.

However, these studies have collectively, highlight the dynamic nature of predictive modelling in glaucoma and stress the importance of comparisons between the logistic, robust (Robit) and Probit regression models to facilitate the improvement on the understanding and management of this

multifaceted condition. Furthermore, this research ought to improve on the existing literatures by comparing the performances of Logistic regression, Probit and Robit regression models in order to determine the most effective model in predicting open-angle Glaucoma diseases. The outcome of the study will provide Bio/medical statisticians, medical researchers, and ophthalmologists to make a more objective assessment of the evolution of open-angle glaucoma (OAG) during tertiary prevention. Likewise, it would also guide researchers with the model more fitted to Glaucoma disease and other related health disease data

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Globally, glaucoma is known to be one of the main causes of irreversible blindness, with millions of people suffering, and increased costs to health systems. Research also suggests that whilst a considerable progress has been made in the development of diagnostic models in detecting glaucoma disease, there is still an unresolved problem of accurate prediction in the control of glaucoma.

While recent studies identified a high demand for increased accuracy and models' ability to generalize the glaucoma diagnosis. Olufemi et al., (2023) employed logistic regression in identifying such risk factors and recommends the use of logistic regression for predicting glaucoma disease, without taking into account other benchmark models. Moreover, there is the concern with demographic distribution in glaucoma and its treatment procedures, which led to the concern regarding population-specific predictive modeling (research collaborative, 2023).

However, current literatures lack sufficient analysis regarding the prediction capabilities of logistic regression, probit and robit regression models for glaucoma diagnosis, and how these models address issues within varied data sets and in the presence of outliers.

Therefore, this study tends to address the gap and improve on Olufemi et al., (2023) by comparing the performance of logistic regression, probit regression and Robit regression models in predicting Glaucoma disease. Hence, by evaluating the models across different datasets, patient characteristics, sample sizes and outlier, the study tends to identify the most effective model with predictive accuracy to enhance glaucoma diagnostic and treatment.

1.3 Aims and Objectives

While the goal of this study aims to investigate the performances of Robit regression, logistic regression and Probit regression Model, in modeling open-angle glaucoma disease, with a particular emphasis on robustness to outliers and overall model efficiency, the specific objectives are to;

- I. Determine the most fitted model for predicting open-angle glaucoma disease;
- II. Investigate the performances of Robit regression in identifying the risk factors for open-angle glaucoma disease, with emphasis on its ability to handle outlier contamination; and
- III. To compare the performance of the model's applicability on real life data and simulated data

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Data collection

While this study seeks to evaluate the performances of logistic regression, Probit regression and Robit regression model in predicting open-angle glaucoma disease. The study employs simulated data for the analysis in this study is and a real-life daily data record of open-angle glaucoma patient characteristic span the year 2022 – 2024 obtained from Makkah Specialist eye hospital Bauchi, using a Quata sampling procedure to draw a sample of 300 patients with Glaucoma disease disorder.

3.2 Variable description

The dynamic variables in this study are taking the following abbreviations.

- Age = *AG*
- Genetic = *GT*
- Diabetes = *DT*
- Hypertension = *HY*
- Gender = *GD*
- Intraocular Pressure = *IOP*

3.2 Logistic Regression Model

Suppose that the observed data consists of n independent observations $\{(x_i, y_i) : i = 1, \dots, n\}$ with a p -dimensional covariate vector x_i and binary response y_i that is either 0 or 1. The logistic regression model is specified by

$$\text{logit}(\text{pr}(y_i = 1|x_i, \beta)) = \ln \frac{\text{pr}(y_i = 1|x_i, \beta)}{1 - \text{pr}(y_i = 1|x_i, \beta)} = x_i' \beta \quad (i = 1, \dots, n) \quad (1)$$

The logistic regression model can also be derived by assuming that there are latent variables $z_i = x_i' \beta + e_i$, where e_i logistic with distribution function

$$f_{\text{logit}}(x) = \frac{\exp\{x\}}{1 + \exp\{x\}} \quad (2)$$

and density function as;

$$f_{\text{logit}}(x) = \frac{\exp\{x\}}{(\exp\{x\})^2} = \frac{1}{(\exp\{-\frac{x}{2}\} + \exp\{\frac{x}{2}\})^2} = \frac{1}{2(1 + \cosh(x))} \quad (3)$$

Where y_i is one if $z_i > 0$ and zero otherwise. Then, the logistic regression model (1) is obtained as the marginal distribution of y_i . The maximum likelihood estimates of β can be obtained using the iterative re-weighted least-squares.

3.3 Probit Regression Model

The probit model is obtained by replacing the logistic distribution for the latent error terms e_i with the standard normal distribution, where $\phi(x)$ and $\Phi(x)$ are the density and distribution functions of the standard normal distribution, respectively. The maximum likelihood estimates of β in the probit model can be obtained using the EM algorithm (Dempster, Laird, and Rubin, 1977) or the PX-EM algorithm (Liu, Rubin, and Wu, 1998). The probit model is given by

$$\text{pr}(y_i = 1|x_i, \beta) = 1 - \text{pr}(y_i = 0|x_i, \beta) = \Phi(x_i' \beta) \quad (i = 1, \dots, n), \quad (4)$$

3.4 Robit Regression Model

The robit regression model for the data $\{(x_i, y_i) : i = 1, \dots, n\}$ is

$$\text{pr}(y_i = 1|x_i, \beta) = 1 - \text{pr}(y_i = 0|x_i, \beta) = F_v(x_i' \beta) \quad (5)$$

Where $F_v(x)$ denotes the cdf of the t random variable with center zero, scale parameter one, and v degrees of freedom. $F_v(x)$ Has the density function

$$f_v(x) \equiv \frac{\Gamma(v+1)/2}{(\pi v)^{\frac{1}{2}} \Gamma(\frac{v}{2}) (1 + \frac{x^2}{v})^{(v+1)/2}} \quad (x \in (-\infty, \infty)) \quad (6)$$

As $v \rightarrow \infty$, the robit (v) model becomes the probit regression model

3.5 Monte Carlo Simulation

The study employs the Monte Carlo simulation equations which as follows

1. Simulating Independent variables; age(age) The categorical variable age is simulated using a multinomial distribution: age Multinomial (n , Page)

Where: Page = [0.4, 0.3, 0.3]. And possible values are {0,1,2}.

Diabetes (diabetes): The categorical variable diabetes is simulated using Bernoulli distribution: Diabetes Bernoulli (P diabetes). Where: P diabetes = 0.5 and the possible values are {1,2}.

2. Simulating dependent variable (glaucoma)

The probability of having glaucoma (Prob-glaucoma) is model as: Prob-glaucoma = min (max (0.2 + 0.5. (Age = 2) + 0.3. (Diabetes = 1), 0), 1)

- (Age =2): indicator variable that equals 1 if age = 2, otherwise 0.

- (Diabetes =1): indicator variable that equals 1 if diabetes = 1, otherwise 0.
- Probabilities are constrained to [0,1].
- The binary outcome glaucoma is then simulated as:

Glaucoma Bernoulli (prob-glaucoma)

3. Monte Carlo Replication

For each Monte Carlo iteration:

1. Generate a dataset of size n by repeating the steps above
2. Split the dataset into training (70%) and testing (30%)
3. Fit model and evaluate performance metrics.

Logistic regression

The logistic regression model predicts the probability:

$$P(\text{glaucoma} = 1/\text{age}, \text{diabetes}) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}}$$

$$\text{Where: } x = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot (\text{age} = 1) + \beta_2 \cdot (\text{age} = 2) + \beta_3 \cdot (\text{diabetes} = 1)$$

Probit Regression

The Probit Regression model predicts the probability:

$$P(\text{Glaucoma} = 1/\text{age}, \text{diabetes}) = \Phi(n)$$

$$\text{Where: } n = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \cdot (\text{age} = 1) + \beta_2 \cdot (\text{age} = 2) + \beta_3 \cdot (\text{diabetes} = 1)$$

And $\Phi(\cdot)$ is the standard normal CDF.

Model accuracy

Accuracy metric: Predictions (\hat{y}) are derived by thresholding probabilities at 0.5

$$\hat{y} = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } P(\text{glaucoma} = 1) > 0.5 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

$$\text{Accuracy is calculated as: Accuracy} = \frac{1}{n_{\text{test}}} \sum_{i=1}^{n_{\text{test}}} 1(\hat{y}_i = y_i)$$

Where 1 is an indicator function that equals 1 if $\hat{y}_i = y_i$ otherwise 0.

Logistic regression model

The logistic regression model predicts the probability $P(Y=1)$ as:

$$P(Y = 1) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-n}}$$

$$\text{Where: } n = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_k X_k$$

β_0 : intercept term

β_1 : Coefficient for predictors X_i

3.6 Measure of performance and selection criteria for the best methods

To select the best model fitting, the study employs Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC). The smaller the value of AIC or BIC, the better the model in fitting. AIC and BIC are defined as follows;

$$AIC = -2 \log p(L) + 2p \tag{12}$$

$$BIC = -2 \log p(L) + p \log(n) \tag{13}$$

Where;

L is the likelihood under the fitted model,

P is the number of parameters used/ in the model,

n is the number of observations / sample size.

ANALYSIS, AND DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Table 1: Model Comparison for Glaucoma Real-life data

Metric	Logistic	Probit	Robit
AIC	92.878	96.498	65.67
BIC	117.728	121.983c	85.98
AUC	0.966	0.966	0.966
Residual Deviance	74.878	78.498	47.67
Significant Predictors	AGE***, IOP***, GNT1**	AGE***, IOP***, GNT1*	IOP.
Fisher Scoring Iterations	16	25	25

Table 1. shows a model performance on real life glaucoma data of sample size 300, where robit regression model indicated a better performance with lower AIC of 65.67 and BIC of 85.67 against Logistic regression with AIC 92.878 and BIC of 117.878, with probit regression having AIC of 96.498 and BIC of 112.498. Where all the variables are significant predictors of Glaucoma disease. The model converges at different points where Logistic model converged faster (16 iterations), Probit and Robit models required more iterations (25 each) all models handled 8 missing observations.

Table 2: Mathematical Models

Model Type	Mathematical Formula
Logistic	$P(Y = 1) = 1 / (1 + e^{(-\beta_0 - \beta_1 X_1 - \dots - \beta_k X_k)})$
Probit	$P(Y = 1) = \Phi(\beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \dots + \beta_k X_k)$
Robit	$P(Y = 1) = F(\beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \dots + \beta_k X_k)$

Where:

- Y is the Glaucoma Status (0 = positive, 1 = negative)
- Φ is the cumulative distribution function of the standard normal distribution
- F is the cumulative distribution function of the student's t-distribution

X_1, \dots, X_k represent the predictor variables (GND, GNT, DBT, HPT, AGE, IOP)

Table 3: Model Summaries of Logistic Regression Results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-value	p-value	Significance
Intercept	9.22075	1.88942	4.880	1.06e-06	***
GND1	0.53543	0.65410	0.819	0.41303	
GNT1	4.08923	1.45244	2.815	0.00487	**
AGE	-0.17257	0.03268	-5.281	1.28e-07	***
IOP	-0.32830	0.05943	-5.524	3.31e-08	***

Table 3. shows the model summary for logistic regression glaucoma real-life data, where the coefficient for the intercept is 9.22075 and the variables GND1 (0.53543), GNT1 (4.08923), Age (-0.17257), and IOP (-0.32830). The coefficients for logistic regression are relatively higher than probit regression but lower than robit regression. The model indicated that Age, Genetic and IOP are significant predictors of Glaucoma disease with (P-values < 0.05) and the negative signs suggests that high ages and IOP are associated with positive glaucoma status.

Table 4: Model summary of Probit Regression Results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-value	p-value	Significance
Intercept	4.598	0.8871	5.183	2.19e-07	***
GND1	0.3037	0.3196	0.950	0.3420	
GNT1	1.793	0.7114	2.520	0.0117	*
AGE	-0.08475	0.01584	-5.350	8.81e-08	***
IOP	-0.1642	0.02223	-7.385	1.52e-13	***

Table 4. shows the model summary for probit regression glaucoma real-life data, where the intercept of the model is 4.598, and the variable GND1 (0.3037), 1 GNT (1.793), AGE (-0.08475) and IOP (-0.1642). The coefficients of the variables in probit regression model are relatively lower than logistic regression and probit regression models. The model also indicated Age, and IOP as significant predictors of Glaucoma disease with very low (P-values < 0.05) and the negative signs suggests that high AGE and IOP are associated with positive glaucoma status.

Table 5: Model summary of Robit Regression Results

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-value	p-value	Significance
Intercept	70.88	43.88	1.615	0.1062	
GND1	-2.460	7.813	-0.315	0.7529	
GNT1	13.20	16.82	0.785	0.4325	
AGE	-0.9038	0.6457	-1.400	0.1616	
IOP	-3.871	2.030	-1.907	0.0566	

Table 5. shows the model summary for probit regression glaucoma real-life data, where the intercept of the model is 70.88, and the variable GND1 (-2.460), 1 GNT (13.20), AGE (-0.9038) and IOP (-3.871). The coefficients of the variables in robit regression model are relatively higher than logistic regression and probit regression models. The model also indicated all variable as not significant predictors of Glaucoma disease with very high (P-values > 0.05) and the negative signs also suggests that high AGE and IOP are associated with positive glaucoma status.

Result for Simulation studies

Table 6: Results of Performance across Sample Sizes without Outliers

Sample Size	Model	MAE	MSE	RMSE	AIC	BIC	AUC
200	Logistic	0.4686	0.2276	0.4771	196.17	207.94	0.6952
	Probit	0.4687	0.2276	0.4771	196.18	207.95	0.6952
	Robit	0.4687	0.2276	0.4771	196.18	207.95	0.6952
400	Logistic	0.4678	0.2344	0.4841	378.79	393.33	0.6367
	Probit	0.4679	0.2346	0.4843	378.76	393.30	0.6367
	Robit	0.4679	0.2346	0.4843	378.76	393.30	0.6367
600	Logistic	0.4728	0.2478	0.4978	543.87	560.04	0.5990
	Probit	0.4728	0.2477	0.4977	543.92	560.08	0.5990
	Robit	0.4728	0.2477	0.4977	543.92	560.08	0.5990

Table 6. show a summary of model performance across different sample sizes without outliers, where the table indicated that logistic regression model performed better in sample size 200, with a slightly lower AIC of 196.17. Where in sample size of 400 probit and Robit regression model has a marginally lower AIC of 378.76 against logistic regression model with AIC 378.79. Subsequently, in sample size of 600 logistic regression model shows a better fit with AIC 543.87 against probit and robit regression model with AIC 54.87. Where in all sample sizes the three models have same AU. The results indicated logistic

regression model has the lowest MAE, MSE and RMSE in sample 200 and 400, where probit and robit regression models has the lowest MAE, MSR and RMSE in sample of 600.

Table 7: Results With 5% Outliers across Sample Sizes

Sample Size	Model	MAE	MSE	RMSE	AIC	BIC	AUC
200	Logistic	0.4686	0.2276	0.4771	196.17	207.94	0.6952
	Probit	0.4687	0.2276	0.4771	196.18	207.95	0.6952
	Robit	0.4687	0.2276	0.4771	196.18	207.95	0.6952
400	Logistic	0.4678	0.2344	0.4841	378.79	393.33	0.6367
	Probit	0.4679	0.2346	0.4843	378.76	393.30	0.6367
	Robit	0.4679	0.2346	0.4843	378.76	393.30	0.6367
600	Logistic	0.4728	0.2478	0.4978	543.87	560.04	0.5990
	Probit	0.4728	0.2477	0.4977	543.92	560.08	0.5990
	Robit	0.4728	0.2477	0.4977	543.92	560.08	0.5990

Table 7. shows a summary of comparative analysis and model performances across three different samples, where logistic regression indicated a better performance with slightly lower AIC of 196.17 and BIC of 207.94, where AUC are same between the three models. Hence, probit and Robit regression models indicated a better performance in sample of 400, with slightly lower AIC of 378.76 and BIC of 393.30 where AUC are same between the three models across sample sizes. Moreover, logistic regression shows a better performance with AIC 543.87 and BIC 560.04 in sample size of 600.

Table 8: Results for Performance across Sample Sizes containing 20% Outliers

Sample Size	Model	MAE	MSE	RMSE	AIC	BIC	AUC
200	Logistic	0.4894	0.2409	0.4908	201.1895	212.9561	0.7121
	Probit	0.4894	0.2409	0.4908	201.1877	212.9543	0.7121
	Robit	0.4894	0.2409	0.4908	201.1877	212.9543	0.7121
400	Logistic	0.4926	0.2476	0.4976	389.2527	403.7919	0.5187
	Probit	0.4926	0.2476	0.4976	389.2531	403.7922	0.5187
	Robit	0.4926	0.2476	0.4976	389.2531	403.7922	0.5187
600	Logistic	0.4959	0.2515	0.5015	580.1936	596.3547	0.5481
	Probit	0.4959	0.2515	0.5015	580.1956	596.3566	0.5481
	Robit	0.4959	0.2515	0.5015	580.1956	596.3566	0.5481

Table 8. display a summary of comparative analysis on model performances where in sample size 200 with 20% outlier probit and Robit regression models indicated a better performance with a slightly lower AIC of 201.1877 and lower BIC of 212.9543, where AUC are same across between the three models. Subsequently, logistic regression model indicated a better performance in sample size of 400 with lower AIC of 403.2527 and BIC 403.7919. Moreover, in sample size of 600, logistic regression indicated a better performance with a slightly lower AIC of 580.1936 and a lower BIC of 596.3547, where AUC are same between the three models. The result show MAE, MSE, RMSE and consistent across models when data contain more outliers.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

In conclusion findings from the study suggest that results remain almost identical to the case without outliers and AUC drops significantly for larger sample sizes, indicating a reduced ability to differentiate between cases and controls. Performance metrics (MAE, MSE, RMSE, AIC, BIC, and AUC) are nearly the same as in the no-outlier condition and confirms that outliers introduce more errors.

The models remain robust against a small number of outliers, suggesting that a 5% contamination does not significantly degrade performance and do not impact the models significantly, meaning they are fairly resilient to minimal noise in the dataset. The models handle minor outliers well (5%) but are highly sensitive to large outliers (20%). Effect of Outliers: Small outliers (5%) have negligible impact, but 20% outliers significantly worsen model accuracy. Larger datasets do not necessarily improve model accuracy,

as seen in the decreasing AUC values. Preprocessing techniques, such as outlier detection and robust regression methods, may be necessary to improve performance when dealing with datasets with significant noise. Logistic Regression is the most stable model overall, especially in larger datasets and under high outlier conditions. Probit and Robit perform slightly better in terms of AIC for small sample sizes, but the difference is negligible. Under extreme noise (20% outliers), Logistic Regression outperforms the others in classification ability.

Moreover, in dealing with real-life glaucoma data robit regression model with the lowest AIC and BIC outperformed both logistic regression with the second lowest and probit regression model with the largest AIC and BIC values. However, while robit regression shows the best model, the logistic and probit models provide more interpretable results. The result indicated that higher values of Age and IOP are associated with positive glaucoma status. Where Genetic (1) category suggest a negative glaucoma status and that both older ages and higher IOP are risk factors for positive open-angle glaucoma disease. Result from simulated data and glaucoma real-life data varies as real-life data provide more insight in predicting glaucoma risk factors. And the result indicated that robit regression model is more suitable and a better model for predicting glaucoma disease. Further study should focused on including additional variables of the risk factors of the open angle glaucoma, and the use of Machine Learning hybrid model.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- I. When using a large sample data that without outlier Logistic regression model is recommended
- II. Probit and robit regression models are recommended for a medium sample size with little percentage of outlier.
- III. Robit regression model is most suitable and better model in predicting open-angle glaucoma disease especially in the presence of outliers.
- IV. While robit regression model outperformed both Logistic regression and probit regression models, the two models provide more interpretable result than the robit regression model.

REFERENCES

- Al-Kahtani, M. A., Awad, A. M., Al-Muammar, A. M., Al-Hazzaa, S. A., & Al-Rajhi, A. A. (2017). Comparison of different machine learning classifiers for open-angle glaucoma with visual field and optical coherence tomography data. *Clinical ophthalmology (Auckland, N.Z.)*, 11, 2021–2029.
- Aljumah, A., Alodhayb, S., Almobarak, F. A., Al-Saikhan, F. I., Ahmad, W., & Al-Khathaami, A. M. (2016). Evaluation and Diagnosis of Glaucoma with Bayesian Network Model. *Journal of Medical Systems*, 40(12), 284.
- Application of Machine Learning Predictive Models for Early Detection of Glaucoma Using Real World Data. (2023). *Applied Sciences*, 13(4), 2445. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app13042445>
- Bali, T.G., Demirtas, K.O., & Lehavy, R. (2008). Testing for autocorrelation in regression residuals: An alternative approach. *Journal of Business & Economic Statistics*, 26(2), 267– 276.
- Bailey, J.N.C., Loomis, S.J., Kang, J.H., Allingham, R.R., Gharahkhani, P., Khor, C.C., Burdon, K.P., Aschard, H., Chasman, D.I., Igo, R.P., Jr. (2011). Risk factors for open angle glaucoma - Analyses using logistic regression. *International Journal of Medical Engineering and Informatics*, 3(3), 203-222. <https://doi.org/10.1504/IJMEI.2011.042867>
- Bragança, C.P., Torres, J.M., Soares, C.P., Macedo, L.O. (2023). Application of Machine Learning Predictive Models for Early Detection of Glaucoma Using Real World Data. *Applied Sciences*, 13(4), 2445. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app13042445>
- DeAngelis, M.M., Lin, R.S., Fareed, M., Huang, J.Y. (2013). A novel hybrid model combining logistic regression with decision tree methods for the prediction of glaucoma progression. *AMIA Annual Symposium Proceedings*. 2013, 273–282.
- Deva, N. C., Insull, E., Gamble, G., & Danesh-Meyer, H. (2014). Risk factors for first presentation of glaucoma with significant visual field loss. *Clinical & experimental ophthalmology*, 42(3), 217–222.

- Gelman, A., Hill, J., & Vehtari, A. (2021). *Regression and other stories*. Cambridge University Press.
- Huber, P. J. (1964). Robust estimation of a location parameter. *The Annals of Mathematical Statistics*, 35(1), 73-101.
- Jeelani, I., Asok Kumar, R., Mark, D., Michael, R., Asokan, R. (2021). Identification of risk factors for glaucoma using random forest approach and exploratory factor analysis. *Eye*. 35(9), 2543-2552.
- Kiani, K., & Arbon, P. (2020). Normality tests for statistical analysis: A guide for non-statisticians. *International Journal of Health Care Quality Assurance*.
- Lange, K. L., Little, R. J. A., and Taylor, J. M. G. (1989), *Robust Statistical Modeling Using the Distribution*, *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, 84, 881-896.
- Liu, C. (2000). Comment on “The Art of Data Augmentation” by Meng and van Dyk. *Journal of Computational and Graphical Statistics*, to Appear.
- Livne, M., Srhoj-Egekher, V., Zajicek, G., et al. (2019). Automatic diagnosis of glaucoma using deep learning. *Translational Vision Science & Technology*. 8(4), 12.
- Ng, W.S., Agarwal, P.K., Sidiki, S., McKay, L., Townend, J., Azuara-Blanco, A. (2016). The effect of socio-economic deprivation on severity of glaucoma at presentation. *British Journal of Ophthalmology*. 100(1), 85-88.
- Pang, G., Shen, C., Cao, L., & Hengel, A. V. D. (2021). Deep learning for anomaly detection: A review. *ACM Computing Surveys (CSUR)*, 54(2), 1-38.
- Panton, H., Goldberg, L. R., & Martin, L. R. (2016). Covariate selection in robust regression for the case-control study design. *Computational Statistics*, 31(4), 1407–1421.
- Sarkedis, D. M., & Meloun, M. (2019). Quantitative structure-retention relationships modeling by robust partial least square regression. *Analytica Chimica Acta*, 1077, 122-129.
- Sarraf, S., DeSouza, E., Anderson, D., Chan, P., & Siu, K. K. (2016). Robust regression technique for small data sets with outliers. *Quantile*, 1(8), 1-13.
- Tham, Y.C., Li, X., Wong, T.Y., Quigley, H.A., Aung, T., Cheng, C.Y. (2014). Global prevalence of glaucoma and projections of glaucoma burden through 2040. *Ophthalmology*. 121(11), 2081-2090.
- Tilling, K., Sterne, J.A., Wolfe, C.D. (2001). Multivariable prognostic models: examining the assumptions and challenges. *Journal of Clinical Epidemiology*. 54(10), 950-957.
- Tun, T.A., Nelson, J., Cordeiro, M.F., Miglior, S., Zheleznyak, L., Nivison-Smith, L. (2020). Evaluation and validation of machine learning techniques for glaucoma diagnosis. *Translational Vision Science & Technology*. 9(2), 7.
- Yousefi, S., R.M. Goldbaum, M.H. Zweig, et al. (2018). Detecting glaucoma progression with multivariate adaptive regression splines. *PLoS One*. 13(7), e0200105.
- Zhou, R., Miller, P., Gordon, J., Kass, M., Lin, M., Peng, M., Li, Y., Feng, F., Liu, J. (2024). Deep learning models to predict primary open-angle glaucoma. *Statistics in Medicine*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sta4.649>